

A descriptive study to assess the knowledge regarding hazards of drug abuse among the male students of selected nursing colleges at Tumkuru, with a view to develop an information booklet

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Abstract: Background: Drug abuse is a social issue, it is not only in India, but the entire world has become a victim of it. The utilization of such wrong things has its very own way of life and history, which differs from nation to nation. The issue of drug misuse is developing at a hazardous rate and in only minimal over a decade it has spread its noxious appendages to pretty much all aspects of globe surmounting practically all hindrances of race, position, belief, religion, sex, education, and socio economic status.

Aims: The aim of the study was to assess the knowledge regarding hazards of drug abuse among male students selected nursing colleges at Tumakuru.

Methodology: The knowledge of students was measured using structured questionnaire from a convenient sample of 60 male student studying at selected nursing colleges Tumakuru. In a descriptive survey design. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Findings The finding of the study indicate that the major findings of the study were out of 60 samples The findings on assessment of knowledge regarding hazards of drug abuse showed that majority 31 (51.66%) of the male students had average knowledge regarding hazards of drug abuse, 28 (46.66%) were having poor knowledge and only 1 (1.66%) had good knowledge regarding hazards of drug abuse.

Statistical analysis using chi-square test was computed to find out the association between knowledge scores male nursing students with selected demographic variables. The computed values were not significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there was no statistically significant association between knowledge and selected demographic variables.

Conclusion: The study concludes that the majority of the male students had average knowledge regarding hazards of drug abuse. This study is effective to identify the knowledge among male students and how to overcome the hazards.

Keywords: knowledge, Drug abuse, Male students.

I. INTRODUCTION

Drug abuse is a social issue, it is not only in India, but the entire world has become a victim of it. The utilization of such wrong things has its very own way of life and history, which differs from nation to nation. The issue of drug misuse is developing at a hazardous rate and in only minimal over a decade it has spread its noxious appendages to pretty much all aspects of the globe surmounting practically all hindrances of race, position, belief, religion, sex, education and socio economic status.¹

Abuse of drugs among youths has turned into a worldwide challenge and furthermore a significant general wellbeing concern and for as far back as two decades there has been an emotional increment in the interest for mediations to address the substance misuse issue. This interest has prompted the improvement of numerous essential, auxiliary and tertiary substance misuse counteractive action programs. June 26, 1992 was pronounced by WHO as the International Day against Drug Abuse and Illicit Trafficking. Moreover, the years 1991-2000 were assigned as the United Nations Decade against Drug Misuse.²

The ancient Indian Vedas mention “somaras,” an alcoholic beverage, as a well spring of joy for gods. Cannabis (Indian hemp) was found in 800 BC. The plant grows wild throughout the foothills of the Himalayas and the adjoining states. The poppy plant (*Papaver somniferum*) and its product - opium - are comparatively of recent introduction. This plant can grow in any part of the country and is also cultivated. It is believed that the use of opium in India began in the 9th century A. D through the influence of Arab traders. During the times of Moghuls, cultivation of the poppy became extensive and an important article of trade with China and other eastern countries.³

Drug abuse is defined as “A maladaptive pattern of substance abuse manifested by recurrent and significant adverse consequences related to the repeated use of substances.”⁴

Drugs most often associated this team includes tobacco, alcohol cannabis barbiturates benzodiazepines cocaine methoqualane opioids and some substituted/amphetamine or even intravenous use of drugs such as heroin have also been reported. A new trend has emerged in drug and substance abuse with youths now taking a cocktail of drugs through injection and often sharing the same needle, which increases their vulnerability to HIV injection.⁵

The drug abuse by young people and there antagonistic results are ending up logically a noteworthy wellbeing concern. Numerous grown-up smokers had started the propensity as youths smoking in young people may likewise be a marker of other unsafe ways of life, for example, commitment in unlawful medication use, liquor utilize mental diseases. The use of substances utilized differed exhausting on the general public and period of youthful. Young people started drugs for various reasons, from interest jucreation to the need to adapt to pressure yet tranquilize above and dependence lead to a mind boggling set of social, medicinal and practical issues with genuine ramifications. Some substance present in effectively accessible items like hack syrups relief from discomfort treatments paste paint, fuel and cleaning liquids are legitimately foxic and frequently manhandled by kids.⁶

Drug abuse has turned into a noteworthy issue in any developing society. It has a solid effect on close to home and family life. Drugs and liquor have an immediate connection to explicitly transmitted infection and AIDS. WHO data (2000) demonstrate that India is high up in the rundown of threat nations due to populace development and high birth rate. Today, individuals are less worried about communism, private enterprise and economism and increasingly stressed over medications, liquor abuse, assault and terrorism.⁷

II. FIGURES GRAPHS AND TABLES

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of knowledge scores male students regarding hazards of drug abuse.

n= 60

Level of knowledge	Score range	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Good (Mean+SD)	20-25	01	1.66
Average (Mean+SD) & (Mean-SD)	8-20	31	51.66
Poor (Mean-SD)	0-7	28	46.66

Findings reveal that majority 31(51.66%) of the male students had average knowledge regarding hazards of drug abuse, 28(46.66%) were having poor knowledge and only 1%(1.66%) had good knowledgeregarding hazards of drug abuse.

Table 2: Association between knowledge scores and selected demographic variables.

S No.	Socio-demographic variables	Good	Average	Poor	χ^2 CAL.VAL	χ^2 TAB VAL	df
	Age						
	18-20	1	14	13	1.17	5.991	2
	21-24	0	17	15			
2	Year of Study						
	First year	0	13	5	6.72	12.592	6
	Second year	0	5	7			
	Third year	1	10	10			
	Fourth year	0	3	6			
3	Place of Stay						
	Home	1	6	9	8.44	12.592	6
	Hostel	0	7	3			
	Paying Guest	0	8	6			
	Relatives' Home	0	3	10			
4	Family						
	Nuclear Family	0	10	9	0.74	9.488	4
	Joint Family	1	18	16			
	Single parent family	0	3	3			
5	Living Status of parents						
	Father a) Alive	1	18	13	6.03	12.592	6
	b) Dead	0	3	0			
	Mother a) Alive	1	10	15			
	b) Dead	0	0	0			
6	Do you have a part time job						
	Yes	1	10	17	5.95	5.991	2
	No	0	21	11			
7	Monthly pocket money						
	Below Rs. 500	0	14	8	8.07	12.592	6
	Rs. 501- 1000	1	5	4			
	Rs. 1001 – 1500	0	8	8			
	Rs. 1501- 2000	0	4	8			
8	Monthly Family Income						
	Rs. 3000 – 5000	0	7	9	3.44	12.592	6
	Rs. 5001 - 7000	0	8	4			
	Rs. 7001 – 9000	1	10	10			
	Rs. 9001 & above	0	6	5			
9	How often do you listen or watch programmes related hazards of drug abuse in tv / radio.						
	Very Often	1	12	2	11.4	12.592	6
	Sometimes	0	6	6			
	Rarely	0	7	12			
	Never	0	6	8			

p<0.05

The findings of table 2 reveal that the variables age, year of study, place of stay, type of family, living status of parents, part time job, monthly pocket money, monthly income of family and frequency of information related to hazards of drug abuse are independent of each other. Here, the chi square calculated value is less than the table value, hence there is no association between knowledge scores and selected demographic variables.

Graph 1: Column graph showing percentage distribution of male students according to age

Graph 1 indicates that the majority 43 (71.66%) of students were 18-20 years old and 17 (28.33%) were of 21-24 years old

Graph 2: Bar graph showing percentage distribution of male students according to year of study

Graph 2 depicts that most of them 34 (56.55%) were studying in second year, 15 (25%) belonged to third year, 6 (10%) belonged to first year and only 5 (8.33%) were from fourth year

Graph3: Doughnut graph showing percentage distribution of male students according to place of study

Graph 3 reveals that majority 35 (58.33%) of students were staying in hostel, 20 (33.33%) stayed at their homes and only 5 (8.33%) were staying as paying guests.

Graph 4: Pie graph showing percentage distribution of male students according to type of family

Graph 4 indicated that 28 (46.66%) students belonged to nuclear families, 19 (31.66%) were in joint families and only 3 (5%) were having single parent

Graph 5: Column graph showing percentage distribution of male students according living status of parents

Graph 5 depicted that majority 57 (95%) students' fathers were alive and 3 (5%) were dead, whereas all students 60 (100%) the mothers were alive

Graph 6: Pie graph showing percentage distribution of male students according to part time job

Graph 6 shows that most of the students 44 (73.33%) did not go for a part time job, whereas 16 (26.66%) were doing some part time jobs

Graph 7: Column graph showing percentage distribution of male students according to monthly pocket money

Graph 7 indicated that majority 32 (53.33%) of the students received pocket money below 500 rs per month, 19 (31.66%) of them received pocket money of Rs. 501- 1000, 7 (11.66%) received around Rs. 1001-1500 and only 2 (3.33%) received Rs. 1501-2000 as their pocket money

Graph 8: Bar graph showing percentage distribution of male students according to monthly income of family

Graph 8 depicts that 24 (40%) of their families were in the range of Rs. 3000-5000, remaining 12 (20%) were equally ranging from Rs. 5001-7000, Rs. 7001-9000 and Rs. 9001 & above respectively

Graph 9: Column graph showing percentage distribution of male students according information from tv /radio

Graph 9 shows that most of them 35 (58.33%) got information sometimes related to hazards of drug abuse from TV/Radio, 13 (21.66%) got rarely the information related to hazards of drug abuse from tv/ radio, 6 (10%) of them information very often and 6 (10%) never got any information from TV/Radio.

III. DISCUSSION

Although present study discussion is focused with the objectives of the study to assess the knowledge regarding hazards of drug abuse among male students of selected nursing colleges of Tumakuru.

Demographic Variables:

In the present study it was found that out of 60 samples, majority 43 (71.66%) of students were 18-20 years old and 17 (28.33%) were of 21-24 years old. These findings were supported by a study⁵⁷ conducted by Kalpana et.al; in Bangalore noted that the students were of the age group between 18-23 years old.

35 (58.33%) of students were staying in hostel, 20 (33.33%) stayed at their homes and only 5 (8.33%) were staying as paying guests. As far as their family was concerned, 28 (46.66%) students belonged to nuclear families, 19 (31.66%) were in joint families and only 3 (5%) were having single parent. Similar findings were noted in a study⁵⁸ conducted by Silas T, et.al; in Pune, where 47 % of the students were staying in hostel, 28% were staying in their homes. 44 % belonged to nuclear families, 52% belonged to joint families respectively.

Most of the students 44 (73.33%) did not go for a part time job, whereas 16 (26.66%) were doing some part time jobs. 32 (53.33%) of the students received pocket money below 500 rs per month, 19 (31.66%) of them received pocket money of Rs. 501- 1000, 7 (11.66%) received around Rs. 1001-1500 and only 2 (3.33%) received Rs. 1501-2000 as their pocket money. Monthly income of family when taken into consideration, 24 (40%) of their families were in the range of Rs. 3000-5000, remaining 12 (20%) were equally ranging from Rs. 5001-7000, Rs. 7001-9000 and Rs. 9001 & above respectively. The findings of the study were similar to a study⁵⁹ conducted by Sheeja et.al; where 12% of samples had monthly income 6000- 9000.

Knowledge regarding hazards of drug abuse

Knowledge scores indicated that majority 31 (51.66%) of the male students had average knowledge regarding hazards of drug abuse, 28 (46.66%) were having poor knowledge and only 1 (1.66%) had good knowledge regarding hazards of drug abuse.

The findings were almost similar to the findings of the study⁵⁹ done by Sheeja et.al; where 48% had poor knowledge about substance abuse, 47% had average knowledge about substance abuse and 05% had good knowledge about substance abuse.

Association of knowledge of Government primary school children with selected demographic variables:

Chi-square test was computed to find out the association between knowledge scores male nursing students with selected demographic variables. Test results were, Chi-square value at (5.991) for age was (1.17), for year of study at (12.592) was (6.72), place of stay was (8.44), for family at (9.488) was (0.74), for living status of parents at (12.592) was (6.03), for part time job at (5.991) was 5.95, for monthly pocket money at (12.592) was 8.07, monthly income was 3.44 and information related to hazards of drug abuse was 11.4 respectively. The computed values were not significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there was no statistically significant association between knowledge and selected demographic variables.

Similar findings were noted in a study⁴¹ conducted by Theou C. et al; where all the variables like age, type of family, monthly income, place of stay were not found to be statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence it was inferred that the present knowledge was independent of all the selected variables.

Limitations

- The present study was limited to nursing college at Tumkur.
- The present study was limited to only 60 male nursing students

IV. RECOMMENDATIONS

Interventions should be aimed at reducing the hazards of drug abuse among male nursing students at selected nursing college. Similar study can be replicated on a large sample to generalize the findings. A comparative study may be conducted between medical and nursing students. A study may be conducted on student-to-student approach in colleges, to have an impact on the health of the community. A descriptive study can be conducted on knowledge of parents regarding hazards of drug abuse.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The study is helpful to find the knowledge of hazards of drug abuse among male nursing students studying selected nursing colleges at Tumkuru, and suggests that interventions focusing to reduce the hazards of drug abuse among male students would contribute to the improvement of their quality of life. Future researches can investigate the effect of various psychological measures to reduce the hazards of drug abuse with the aim of improving their overall quality of life.

Ethical Clearance

Ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional ethical committee of Shree Siddaganga Institute of Nursing Sciences and Research Center, Tumkuru

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Conflict of Interest: Nil

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